

GO-FORWARD

GEOTHERMAL EXPLORATION AND **O**PTIMIZATION THROUGH
FORWARD MODELING AND RESOURCE DEVELOPMENT

D2.2: Comparison between open-source SFM tools vs. DionisosFlow, and
data assimilation capacities

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List of Abbreviations

DFM	diagenesis forward modelling
EU GA	EU Grant Agreement
FFM	fracture network forward modelling
ML	Machine Learning
PC	Project Coordinator
POS	Probability of Success
PR	Periodic Report
PSC	Project Scientific Coordinator
SC	Steering Committee
SFM	stratigraphic forward modelling
SRL	Societal Readiness Level
TL	Task Leader
VOI	Value of Information
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leaders

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1 Executive Summary

The present deliverable documents the outcomes of Task 2.2 of the GO-Forward project, which aimed to develop and compare open-source Stratigraphic Forward Modelling (SFM) tools with the commercial software DionisosFlow, while also evaluating data assimilation and calibration capabilities for application in geothermal reservoir modelling.

Work Package (WP) 2 serves as the methodological foundation for the GO-Forward project. The primary objective of Task 2.2 was the development of fast, surrogate-based open-source SFM codes capable of reproducing facies distributions in 2D and 3D across continental and marine, siliciclastic and carbonate depositional environments at regional scales. A key emphasis was placed on computational performance and simplified user interaction to facilitate data assimilation and calibration against data-rich datasets. The commercial software DionisosFlow served as the benchmark for comparison, in line with its planned utilisation in Task 3.1 for regional-scale modelling.

1.1 Methodology and Work Performed

An extensive review of existing SFM software was conducted, evaluating both commercial and open-source solutions. The assessed tools included DionisosFlow, SedSimple, pyBadlands, CarboCAT, CarboCATLite, and CarboKitten. Based on this evaluation, CarboKitten, which is a Julia-based open-source implementation of CarboCAT, was identified as the most promising platform for further development.

For siliciclastic systems the pyBadlands codebase was harmonised to Python ≥ 3.12 , enabling full cross-platform compatibility, and performance-enhanced using NUMBA/JIT compilation. Benchmark tests against the legacy Linux implementation confirmed numerical equivalency, with improved runtimes. Despite successful validation, the pre- and post-processing framework was assessed as insufficiently streamlined for direct integration into the GO-Forward workflow in its current form.

For carbonate settings the Eclepens case study in Switzerland (Jurassic carbonate platform) served as the primary test site. Development activities encompassed:

- Numerical modelling: Development of a Python-based algorithm for generating 3D point cloud representations of isolated carbonate build ups
- Visualization: Integration of Blender Geometry Nodes for advanced 3D visualization
- Code extensions: Significant enhancements to CarboCATLite and CarboKitten, including time-dependent subsidence, depth- and time-controlled production scaling, 2D sinusoidal wave fields, rule-based facies classification, and advanced visualization tools
- Data assimilation: Implementation of Morris screening and Monte Carlo simulations for sensitivity analysis and uncertainty quantification

Key findings

1. DionisosFlow remains the preferred tool for regional-scale modelling due to its mature functionality combined with a well-established user-friendly graphical interface that facilitates model parameterisation and scenario testing.
2. CarboKitten has emerged as the most capable open-source alternative, offering:
 - Spatiotemporal subsidence control;
 - Decoupled time- and depth-dependent production control for each carbonate factory;
 - Bidirectional and temporally variable wave forcing;

- Advanced visualisation of 3D model results (fence diagrams, maps, chronostratigraphic columns);
 - Export of quantitative metrics for calibration and sensitivity analysis.
3. Hierarchical Multi-Scale Workflow: A two-stage modelling framework was established and validated, wherein DionisosFlow defines regional-scale depositional architecture and CarboKitten resolves reservoir-scale facies heterogeneity. This hierarchical approach was validated against the Eclepens case study (Oxfordian carbonate platform, Swiss Jura Mountains), demonstrating that the open-source tools produce geologically credible results broadly comparable to DionisosFlow outputs.
 4. Data assimilation remains challenging. Sensitivity analysis reveals complex, nonlinear interactions between parameters, with high uncertainties in basin forcing (subsidence, bathymetry), production rates, colonisation windows, and disintegration rates. Manual calibration is insufficient in this complex context the utilisation of AI-driven optimisation is required to address these challenges.

1.2 Recommendations

A key collaborative relationship within Task 2.2 is the partnership with the MindTheGap project, an EU-funded Horizon Europe ERC Starting Grant (project no. 101041077) entitled "*Quantifying the completeness of the stratigraphic record and its role in reconstructing the tempo and mode of evolution.*" This collaboration centres on the shared development of CarboKitten, an open-source carbonate stratigraphic forward modelling tool originally developed under the MindTheGap initiative. Within GO-Forward, significant extensions were made to the CarboKitten codebase. In recognition of this joint development effort, a formal pull request has been submitted to the official MindTheGap CarboKitten GitHub repository, proposing the integration of all GO-Forward code extensions into the main upstream codebase. The integration of machine learning methods for automated calibration and uncertainty quantification, is a key priority for future phases of GO-Forward. The continuation of this collaboration, especially of shared algorithmic development, will significantly benefit both projects.

1.3 Conclusion

Task 2.2 has established essential foundations for stratigraphic modelling within the GO-Forward project. The further development of CarboKitten provides a scientifically robust, publicly accessible alternative to commercial software, enabling future research in geothermal reservoir characterisation while reducing dependency on proprietary solutions.

2 Introduction

Work package 2 is designed to provide the methodological basis for other work packages by developing and testing methods to facilitate the GO-Forward workflow.

This includes, among others, building machine learning (ML) models which help to quantify relevant calibration parameters for the modelling workflow, such as – lithofacies and seismic facies for stratigraphic forward modelling, or porosity and classification of mineral phases for diagenetic forward modelling. Being carried out in the first 24 months of GO-Forward project lifetime, the first reporting period covers most tasks from the WP, described per work package task in the following section.

The focus of WP 2 is to develop enabling methods and software functionalities beyond the state of the art that streamline the GO-Forward coupled forward stratigraphic, diagenetic, and fracture modelling workflow (SFM, DFM, and FFM, respectively). The purpose of these developments is to obtain better predictions of key input parameters for SFM, DFM, and FFM by leveraging ML techniques as well as for key parameters for geothermal flow performance assessment models and induced seismicity in siliciclastic, carbonate and fractured basement geological settings.

The objective of Task 2.2 was the development of (fast and surrogate) SFM open-source codes that allow the reproduction, in 2D but ideally also in 3D, of facies distributions through time in both continental and marine, siliciclastic and carbonate depositional environments at regional scale. The primary focus was on enhancing computational performance and reducing complexity in user interaction for data assimilation/calibration capabilities to data-rich datasets.

The results obtained using the commercial software (DionisosFlow from Beicip-Franlab) will be used as a benchmark in Task 3.1. The resulting 2D or 3D transects will be compared to real data and the DionisosFlow benchmark outcome. In addition, the code and inter-usability of input/output data, as well as grid formats, will be reviewed and improved. The 2D or 3D transects resulting from DionisosFlow will be compared and calibrated to facies logs or sections from well-logs or seismic sections.

3 SFM Open-Source Codes

An extensive review of existing codebases for SFM was performed by all task partners. Codebases were evaluated and summarised in Table 1 with main features and required input parameters. It should be noted that this list is not exhaustive but features the main software stacks and codebases used for SFM, both in siliciclastic and carbonate settings.

Based on this list, open-source codes with high potential for extension and adaptation to the GO-Forward requirements were identified. For carbonate systems, code developments were first implemented for CarboCATLite and later adapted for CarboKitten when its codebase attained sufficient maturity. Further, the transition from CarboCATLite to CarboKitten is motivated by the underlying programming language. While the codebase for CarboCATLite is open source, it is written in Matlab, which is not inherently open source, as a user needs to have a commercial Matlab license to run the code. CarboKitten on the other hand is written in Julia, a relatively novel high performance programming language with an approachable syntax.

Table 1 WP2 - compilation of stratigraphic forward modelling software

Codebase name	License and code availability	Main features
DionisosFlow part of OpenFlowSuite by Beicip-Franlab	Commercial. Comes with a graphical user interface.	Processes in continental (river) to deep marine basin settings. Siliciclastics, carbonate, evaporite factories Basin to reservoir scale Processes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Slope driven, wave action transport and deposition • Water transport • Eustasy • Erosion rates • Dissolution (emergence) • Diffusion • Ecological factors on sediments production (Temp, salinity, depth, substrate) • Compaction NOT: automatic calibration to well data, uncertainty related to input data
SedSimple Developed and hosted by Westchase software corporation	open source under GPL-3. Downloadable from https://wsoftc.com/software (login required)	Siliciclastics, Carbonate factories <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Slope failure • Turbidites/gravity flows • Wave/storm action • Fluid flow • Loading/isostacy • Erosion rates • Carbonate factories • Compaction
GPM – geological process modelling software Part of Petrel E&P software platform by SLB	Commercial.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Basin-scale 3D • Fluvial channel dynamics and overbank deposition, river plume deposition, open marine currents, wave resuspension, nearshore wave induced longshore and crossshore transport
SimClast	Not clear. Fortran code published as supplementary material to Dalman & Weltje (2012), but with no license file	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Basin-scale 3D

<p>See (Dalman and Weltje 2012) https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cageo.2011.05.014</p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fluvial channel dynamics and overbank deposition, river plume deposition, open marine currents, wave resuspension, nearshore wave induced longshore and crossshore transport
<p>pyBadlands see (Salles et al. 2018) https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0195557</p>	<p>Open source Under GPL 3 Hosted on github https://github.com/badlands-model</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sediment transport over geological time • Reworking of marine sediments • Development of coral reef systems
<p>CarboCAT & CarboCATLite See (Burgess 2013)</p>	<p>Open source CarboCAT under GPL-2.0 hosted on github https://github.com/csdms-contrib/carbocat</p> <p>CarboCATLite under Apache 2 hosted on github https://github.com/MindTheGap-ERC/CarboCATLite</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Carbonate lithofacies calculation and its spatial distribution → accumulation of heterogeneous carbonate strata
<p>CarboKitten See (Hidding et al. 2025) https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-2025-4561</p>	<p>Open source Under GPL 3 on github https://github.com/MindTheGap-ERC/CarboKitten.jl</p>	<p>Julia reimplementations of CarboCAT.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Features: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. carbonate production model 2. cellular automation for spatial heterogeneous carbonate strata (taken from CarboCAT) 3. finite difference transport model
<p>ClinoformNet See (Gao et al. 2023) https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-16-2495-2023</p>	<p>Open source Hosted on github, but NO license provided https://github.com/huigcig/ClinoformNet</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uses pybadlands to simulate 3D clinoform stratigraphy • Runs stochastic SFM (via pyBadlands) • Applies rock-physics relations to create synthetic seismic-style clinoform data • Automatically creates labeled sets (e.g. topset/bottomset) for data

4 Development of Open-source SFM

4.1 Clastics

For stratigraphic forward modelling of clastic systems, pyBadlands was evaluated as an open-source alternative to DionisosFlow. The evaluation of pyBadlands is briefly reported in the subsections below.

4.1.1 PyBadlands capabilities

Badlands (Salles et al., 2018) is an open-source Python-based code (and can be used to simulate:

- hillslope processes (linear & non-linear diffusion),
- fluvial incision (Stream Power Law, Transport Capacity Law)
- sediment transport and deposition,
- wave-induced longshore drift transport,
- reef growth and carbonate platform formation,
- submarine gravity currents (turbidity currents),
- spatially and temporally varying tectonic (horizontal + vertical displacements) and
- effects of climate changes (rainfall) and/or sea-level fluctuations

The source code of Pybadlands is in: [badlands-model/badlands: Basin and Landscape Dynamics model](#). Companion routines for pre and postprocessing are in [badlands-model/badlands-companion: Badlands pre & post-processing](#).

Badlands includes various teaching and benchmark example repositories. In this report we consider [badlands-model/badlands-teaching: Teaching repo for badlands](#)

4.1.2 PyBadlands code harmonization

The forementioned version of the pyBadlands (model) code runs only on linux or unix and is dependent on f90 and c code. The different code bases are not harmonized to most recent python versions and are incompatible to run under windows.

As a critical step for evaluation, we harmonized the code base to python \geq 3.12, and made the code fully python, and enhanced performance by using NUMBA and JIT. Furthermore, we included small 3D visualization code for the results, as original visualization capabilities of badlands are not portable to windows.

We performed two benchmark comparisons on the results of modified code and the original linux output.

4.1.3 Benchmark Delta

The first benchmark considers a marginal slope and shelf and hinterland plain and plateau.

Figure 1 Initial setup of Delta benchmark model

Fully Python - Windows	Legacy Badlands - f90/c - Docker Linux
Runtime: 47s	Runtime: 55s

Figure 2 comparison of outcomes for delta benchmark of modified code (left) and original code (right). Lowermost row is accumulation of different sediment facies at specific locations across the cross section

4.1.4 Benchmark Basin

The second benchmark considers a basin with sloping flanks.

Figure 3 Initial setup of Basin benchmark model

Windows	Docker Linux
Runtime: 4m20s	Runtime: 7m48s

Figure 4 comparison of outcomes for Basin benchmark of modified code (left) and original code (right)

4.1.5 Pybadlands evaluation

The (modified) code evaluation was successful. The pre and postprocessing code base is rather complex and not well suited in its present form to be used in workflows of project partners in GO-Forward.

4.2 Carbonates

Code development for carbonate systems was directed towards two main objectives: (i) the creation of lightweight computational tools for simulating, forecasting, and visualising the spatial distribution and morphological characteristics of isolated carbonate build-ups, and (ii) the extension of existing SFM open-source code frameworks.

DionisosFlow utilises a diffusion-based modelling approach to simulate sediment transport along topographic gradients and in-situ carbonate production. However, within the carbonate domain, DionisosFlow is limited by its inability to account for the stochastic evolution of carbonate strata (e.g.: random distribution of patch reefs) within a single facie. This limitation is of direct consequence for the case studies addressed in this project. In the Upper Jurassic Malm section from German case studies (see WP 3), reservoir facies are primarily governed by isolated buildups. Comparable features are observed in the Devonian carbonates at the north-west Germany test site (WP 4). Consequently, substantial efforts have been made to complement the results obtained from DionisosFlow with open-source workflows.

4.2.1 Isolated Carbonate Build-ups

Modelling isolated carbonate build-ups, such as microbial bioherms, presents a series of fundamental challenges that distinguish it from conventional siliciclastic or layered carbonate reservoir modelling.

Isolated carbonate build-ups exhibit highly irregular and variable three-dimensional geometries. Their plan-view shape, height, and lateral extent are difficult to characterise from outcrop data alone, which is typically limited to two-dimensional cross-sectional observations. A simple geometric approximation, such as a hemisphere or cylinder, is often insufficient to reproduce the natural variability observed in outcrop, necessitating more sophisticated stochastic modelling approaches.

The spatial arrangement of build-ups across a carbonate ramp exerts fundamental control on reservoir connectivity and fluid flow behaviour. However, direct quantification of build-up distribution is severely limited by outcrop accessibility and the inherently fragmentary nature of exposed sections. Conditioning data, such as build up density, spacing, and lateral continuity are often only derivable from 2D cross-sections, introducing significant uncertainty into the three-dimensional model.

Where individual build-ups coalesce, composite structures form with complex, amalgamated geometries. These merged bodies create heterogeneous internal architectures that are challenging to replicate numerically. The degree of build-up amalgamation and inter-build-up facies distribution directly controls reservoir connectivity. Isolated build-ups surrounded by tight facies may form disconnected reservoir bodies, whereas coalesced composite build-ups can create laterally extensive, connected reservoir zones. Accurately capturing this connectivity in a numerical model is critical for reliable reservoir performance prediction but remains challenging given the limited subsurface data typically available.

The stochastic nature of build-up placement and size distribution introduces inherent uncertainty into the model. Multiple equally probable realizations may yield significantly different connectivity scenarios, requiring ensemble-based modelling approaches to adequately quantify reservoir uncertainty.

4.2.2 Numerical Modelling of Isolated Build-up Geometries

A Python-based numerical modelling algorithm was developed to generate three-dimensional point cloud representations of isolated carbonate build ups distributed across a carbonate ramp. The script constitutes a Python translation of an original MATLAB code written by (Winterleitner 2015). The model domain is user-defined and build-up centres are randomly distributed within this domain using a

stochastic placement algorithm. To ensure a geologically realistic spatial arrangement, a minimum inter-build-up distance constraint is enforced, preventing unrealistic clustering of bioherm centers, however, overlapping of taller structures is allowed.

Individual carbonate structures are approximated as hemispheres, with radii randomly assigned within a user-defined range. The three-dimensional surface geometry of each build-up is discretised using spherical coordinates, with azimuthal (α) and elevation (β) angles sampled at 10° intervals over the upper hemisphere ($0^\circ \leq \alpha \leq 360^\circ$, $0^\circ \leq \beta \leq 90^\circ$). Surface point coordinates are computed accordingly using standard spherical-to-Cartesian transformations. To account for coalesced build-up geometries, where individual build-ups overlap, an intersection detection algorithm identifies all build-up pairs whose centre-to-centre distance is less than the sum of their respective radii. Surface points of a given build-up that fall within the volume of an adjacent, intersecting hemisphere are subsequently removed, effectively merging the overlapping bodies into coherent composite structures. This approach reproduces the irregular, amalgamated geometries (Figure 5). The resulting point cloud, comprising the X, Y, and Z coordinates of all valid surface points, is exported as a plain text file for subsequent import and visualisation in three-dimensional modelling environments.

Figure 5: (left) point cloud of coalesced build-ups, (right) surface representation of build-up point cloud

The presented Python code is a simple stochastic method to model the complexity of carbonate build-up facies with their inherent complex geometries and connectivity. The resulting point clouds and triangulated surfaces can be used to guide detailed reservoir modelling by providing spatial context (e.g.: variogram calculations etc.).

4.2.3 Blender Node System

Blender is a free, open-source 3D creation suite developed and maintained by the Blender Foundation. It offers a comprehensive set of tools encompassing 3D modelling, animation, rendering and scripting, making it a compelling alternative to proprietary software. Its Python-based API further extends its capabilities, allowing researchers to automate workflows and integrate Blender into custom data visualisation pipelines. The accessibility of Blender, being freely available across Windows, macOS, and Linux platforms, has contributed to its growing adoption in academic and research environments.

A notable feature of Blender is its Geometry Nodes system. Geometry Nodes is a node-based, procedural modelling framework that allows users to create and manipulate geometry through a visual programming interface, without the need for manual modelling or complex scripting. The procedural nature of Geometry Nodes offers significant advantages. Complex geometries and repetitive structures can be generated algorithmically based on defined parameters, ensuring reproducibility and consistency across datasets. Furthermore, models can be dynamically updated by modifying input parameters, enabling efficient iteration and adaptation of visualisations without rebuilding geometry from scratch. The system supports a wide range of operations, including point

distribution, mesh manipulation, and instance generation. This flexibility is particularly suitable for tasks such as visualising large datasets and spatial distributions, generating structural models and the automatised generation of repetitive geometric patterns.

The Geometry Node system illustrated in Figure 6 is a simple 4 stage iteration of distributing isolated structures onto a grid, based on the principles of the build-up python code. The user can define various shapes of geometry (e.g.: hemispheres, ellipsoids or more complex geometries), size distributions and density functions of the randomly distributed elements. A critical feature of the system is its handling of geometric overlap between adjacent primitives. Rather than enforcing mutual exclusion, the framework permits controlled overlapping of meshes, which results in the emergence of complex amalgamated structures. This approach more accurately reflects the biological reality of bioherm growth, wherein adjacent carbonate producing colonies frequently coalesce to form complex, amalgamated structures, such as clusters and more elongated chain structures. The degree of structural complexity can be modulated through the overlap tolerance parameter, which controls the maximum permitted overlap of adjacent elements before triggering mesh boolean operations.

The initial iteration establishes the foundational nucleation pattern which can be regarded as incipient build-up growth, illustrated in Figure 7.A. The subsequent three Geometry Node iterations further distribute user defined shapes onto the previous meshes, mimicking stages of bioherm evolution (Figure 7.B). For each iteration, distribution density functions and shape parameters (plan-view shape, size, height etc.) are user defined. The final step in the Geometry Nodes system is the meshing of the coalesced structures. The remeshing algorithm in Blender Geometry Nodes system allows the generation of one single triangulated mesh representing the upper encapsulating surface of the bioherm model. The resulting mesh can then be exported as text-based point cloud or as triangulated surface in Wavefront OBJ file format. The latter is an open, text-based standard for exchanging 3D model geometries. The rendering tools allow for a high-resolution photorealistic visualisation of the build-up facies (Figure 7.C-E).

Figure 6: Geometry Node setup

4.2.3.1 Application

The Blender Geometry Node framework constitutes a lightweight, computationally efficient tool for rapid prototyping and modelling of isolated carbonate build-ups. Building upon the algorithmic principles of the Python code, this pipeline implements a multi-stage iterative architecture for carbonate build-up generation with advanced visualisation and export capabilities. Within the Go-Forward geological modelling workflow, this framework serves several distinct applications:

- Bathymetric Constraints for Carbonate Production Modelling

The build-up point cloud may be utilised as property map representing initial bathymetric conditions within the DionisosFlow modelling environment. This integration provides direct geometric constraints on the spatial distribution and elevation of carbonate build-ups, thereby informing carbonate production and enabling more realistic simulation of carbonate platform development.

- Reservoir Modelling and Static Model Construction

The triangulated surface meshes are directly compatible with industry-standard reservoir modelling software. These surfaces facilitate:

Surface-based facies modelling: Boundary surfaces defining the three-dimensional distribution of reefal facies within static reservoir models.

Variogram calculation: Geometric data establishing spatial correlation structures that underpin stochastic reservoir modelling approaches.

- Multiple Point Statistics and Uncertainty Assessment

The framework's capacity for rapid generation of synthetic build-up geometry databases supports Multiple Point Statistics (MPS) workflows. Multiple realisations with varying input parameters enable construction of training image libraries that capture morphological variability, facilitating assessment of model uncertainty and evaluation of alternative geological interpretations.

- Visualisation for Hypothesis Testing and Communication

The integrated high-resolution visualisation capabilities enable visual comparison of generated geometries with outcrop analogues, seismic interpretations, or subsurface data, facilitating hypothesis evaluation and model validation. Publication-quality imagery further supports effective dissemination of modelling results to both technical and non-technical audiences.

Figure 7: Visualisation of Geometry Node results:(A-B) mesh of incipient and 4th generation, (C-D) rendered visualisation, (E) visualisation of build-up facies in shallow marine setting

4.2.4 Eclepens Case Study

The Eclepens case study (Upper Jurassic carbonate platform, Swiss Jura) was selected as the primary test site for benchmarking carbonate open-source software vs. DionisosFlow results due to several key factors. It is representative of carbonate platform systems relevant to geothermal reservoir characterisation in the Go-Forward project area and serves as a direct analogue to subsurface Upper Jurassic carbonates. Furthermore, comprehensive geological data are available, including sedimentological logs, facies descriptions, and a well-established stratigraphic framework. Importantly, the carbonate system of the Jurassic platform is well understood, providing robust geological constraints that allow for reliable model calibration and validation of the developed SFM tools.

4.2.4.1 Geological Overview of Case Study

During the Middle to Late Oxfordian, the Swiss Jura Mountains region was occupied by a wide, carbonate-dominated shallow shelf (Barron et al. 1980). Platform morphology was controlled by differential subsidence along reactivated basement fault systems, with very shallow environments prevailing to the north and deeper epicontinental basins developing to the south. Episodic siliciclastic input was supplied by the erosion of Hercynian crystalline massifs in the hinterland, with vertical basement movements accommodated by plastic deformation of underlying Triassic evaporites (Allenbach 2002).

Interpreted depositional environments encompass a range of marginal-marine to shallow subtidal settings, including freshwater lakes, tidal flats, shallow lagoons, ooid shoals, and coral reefs. The lithological record is dominated by limestones, with marly intervals and dolomites occurring sporadically throughout the succession. Major facies shifts are primarily attributed to metre-scale sea-level fluctuations driven by the orbital short eccentricity cycle (~100 ka). Synsedimentary tectonics generated differential accommodation by creating structurally controlled depressions, in which argillaceous sediments preferentially accumulated, and structural highs, upon which ooid shoals and carbonate islands preferentially developed.

Autocyclic processes, most notably the lateral migration of ooid and bioclastic shoals, contributed additional complexity to the sedimentary record. Climate-driven variations in terrestrial runoff modulated siliciclastic and dissolved nutrient input to the platform. Coral reef communities responded to elevated nutrient concentrations through progressive replacement by microbialite-dominated assemblages, ultimately resulting in their complete smothering by siliciclastic influx (Dupraz and Strasser 1999, 2002)

Six principal facies categories have been identified: emerged land, lake and beach; tidal flat; restricted lagoon; open lagoon; ooid shoal; and coral reef. Lateral facies changes over short distances and rapid vertical transitions are characteristic of the platform, reflecting its highly dynamic depositional nature (Samankassou et al. 2003). Depositional sequences are hierarchically organised at three scales, with small-scale sequences of approximately 100 ka and medium-scale sequences of approximately 400 ka duration, corresponding to the Milankovitch short and long eccentricity cycles, respectively. Sea-level fluctuation amplitudes associated with the 100 ka cycle are estimated at a few metres (Pittet et al. 2000; Strasser et al. 2004). The 20 ka precessional cycle is locally recorded but frequently overprinted by autocyclic processes. Ooid shoals preferentially developed during transgressive systems tracts, while coral reefs are more commonly associated with highstand deposits. Platform evolution was governed by the interplay of four principal mechanisms. Synsedimentary block-faulting created a compartmentalised system of structural highs and depressions, controlling the preferential development of reefs and shoals on elevated areas. High-frequency orbital forcing drove sea-level fluctuations that controlled vertical facies evolution. Climate changes modulated terrestrial runoff and nutrient input, resulting in the progressive replacement of coral reefs by microbialites prior to their smothering by siliciclastics (Dupraz and Strasser 1999, 2002). Autocyclic processes, including lateral migration of sediment bodies, locally overprinted the allocyclic stratigraphic signal.

The Eclépens dataset comprises well data from the three key wells of the project: Eclépens-1, Essertines-1, and Treycovagnes-1. The area is supported by a recently acquired and interpreted 3D seismic survey, which significantly contributed to constraining the geological modelling carried out by the SGE project partners. The wells have an extensive petrophysical log suite. Eclépens-1 has detailed core studies, and Treycovagnes-1 has core-based fracture measurements. The dataset also includes spatial data layers (maps, rasters, and georeferenced satellite imagery), plus geological horizons and fault interpretations in depth domain.

Figure 8: Eclepens reservoir model: (left) Horizon model with offset wells, (right) structural model

4.2.4.2 SFM input parameter definitions

During the Jurassic period, reef ecosystems were predominantly characterised by coral-dominated assemblages (Löser et al. 2024), with significant contributions from siliceous sponges and stromatoporoids (Nembrini et al. 2021). Additional reef framework constituents, frequently documented within Swiss Jurassic limestone successions, include calcareous algae (encompassing both chlorophytes and rhodophytes), bryozoans, oysters, and brachiopods, all of which are interpreted as substantial contributors to biotic carbonate production. Abiotic carbonate components during the Jurassic were primarily represented by ooid-peloid grainstones, alongside meteoric calcretes, the latter of which formed under subaerial exposure conditions associated with relative sea-level lowstands (Nembrini et al. 2021). These abiotic constituents constitute an integral component of the overall carbonate budget and must be considered in the reconstruction of Jurassic carbonate systems.

Carbonate production rates exhibit considerable variability as a function of biotic assemblage composition and prevailing environmental conditions. The majority of calcareous organisms, including scleractinian corals, demonstrate potential carbonate production rates on the order of 10^4 g CaCO_3 m^{-2} yr^{-1} , with entire reef systems yielding comparable magnitudes. Gross primary productivity within coral reef ecosystems typically ranges between 300 and 5000 g C m^{-2} yr^{-1} (Lewis 1977), while net carbonate production attributable to corals spans from 1 to 25 kg m^{-2} yr^{-1} .

Among other significant carbonate-producing organisms, coralline crustose algae contribute between 0.1 and 2.5 kg m^{-2} yr^{-1} , while *Halimeda*, employed here as a proxy for charophytes, yields production rates ranging from 0.03 to 2.2 kg m^{-2} yr^{-1} . Foraminifera and molluscs represent comparatively minor contributors, with production rates of 0–2.5 kg m^{-2} yr^{-1} and 0–0.6 kg m^{-2} yr^{-1} , respectively (Cornwall et al. 2023). Rudist-dominated communities, particularly those exhibiting dense growth fabrics, are estimated to produce between 4.6 and 28.5 kg m^{-2} yr^{-1} of carbonate (Steuber 2000). For rocky-bottom communities, the biogenic silica production rate of siliceous sponges is estimated at a mean value of 0.021 kg Si m^{-2} yr^{-1} (Maldonado et al. 1999). Stromatoporoids are assumed to exhibit carbonate production rates analogous to those of modern coral reef systems (Kiesling et al. 2002).

Depth cutoffs for organism survival represent a critical model parameter. Hermatypic corals are generally confined to water depths of less than 20–25 m, while rudist reefs, by analogy to modern coral reefs, are interpreted to have developed at depths of 30–50 m or less. Coralline crustose algae and *Halimeda* are predominantly restricted to the upper photic zone, typically within 20–30 m and 40 m depth, respectively. Stromatoporoids are similarly interpreted as shallow-water reef builders, occupying depths broadly comparable to modern coral reef systems (Kershaw et al., 2019). Marine molluscs, while distributed across the full depth range, contribute most significantly to carbonate production in shallow environments.

Inorganic carbonate production on shallow tropical platforms ranges from 1 to 3 kg CaCO₃ m⁻² yr⁻¹, locally exceeding 4–5 kg m⁻² yr⁻¹ in coral-dominated reef fronts, while abiotic precipitation in evaporitic environments reaches 1–5 kg m⁻² yr⁻¹. Sediment transport parameters, informed by (Masiero et al. 2021), employ transportable sediment fractions of 0.4–0.85 for low-to-medium energy regimes and 0.9–0.95 for high-energy systems.

4.2.5 Eclepens Dionisos base case model development

The DionisosFlow base case model was developed using an iterative approach to achieve optimal model fit, with the Eclepens reservoir model serving as a reference. The initial bathymetry of the FSM model was extended beyond the reservoir model boundaries by applying kriging geostatistical interpolation, utilizing two offset wells (Essertines-1 and Treycovagnes-1) as anchor points. This ensured accurate representation of sediment transport processes within the reservoir domain. The initial bathymetric surface was constructed based on seismic horizon interpretation, followed by 4D restoration. The restoration process included horizon flattening that honoured the existing fault network (e.g., active normal faults) and adjusted the bathymetry to the paleodepths corresponding to the depositional environment. Model parameters are summarised in Table 2, and sediment classes are listed in Table 3. Accommodation space variation was simulated using the Haq long-term sea level curve for the Upper Jurassic. The base case model is illustrated in Figure 9 and Figure 10.

Table 2: Eclepens Base Case modelling parameters

Parameters	Values
Model size	201.64 km ²
Cell dimension	200 x 200 m
Number of cells	71 x 72
Total simulation time	12.3 myr
Time step	100 kyr
Subsidence rate	28 m Ma ⁻¹
Maximum wave base	28.15 m
Maximum wave energy flux	181.71 kW m ⁻¹

Table 3: Eclepens Base Case modelled sediment classes

Modelled sediment class	Maximum production rate (m Ma ⁻¹)	Wave energy flux (kW m ⁻¹)	Diffusion coefficient (km ² ka ⁻¹)	Transformation rates (m Ma ⁻¹)
Reworked grains	10		0.005	0
Carbonate muds	15	≤ 30	0.05	0
Microbial	1		0.00001	50
Corals	50	≥ 30	0.0001	100
Ooids	50	≥ 35	0.0001	100

Figure 9: Dionisos Eclepens Base Case Model illustrating initial bathymetry (a), sea-level curve (b), production profiles (c) and cross-section model results (d).

4.2.6 CarboCAT and CarboCATLite: A Cellular Automata Model of Heterogeneous Carbonate Strata

One of the goals of GO-forward is to develop open-source codes to model 2D and ideally also 3D facies distributions in various depositional environments. In this project, Task 2.2 partners contribute to this objective by further developing open-source alternatives to DionisosFlow (an industry-standard commercial SFM tool) such as CarboCAT and CarboKitten to perform stratigraphic forward modelling for carbonates.

The methodology was structured into distinct stages: (i) integration of commercial code, DionisosFlow and open-source code, CarboCATLite into a multi-scale modelling workflow; (ii) extension of CarboCATLite to enhance its geological realism and flexibility so that it can operate independently of DionisosFlow inputs; (iii) evaluation and extension of functionalities of another open-source code, CarboKitten, to enhance model output; (iv) development of software interfaces to facilitate the transfer of SFM outputs into downstream diagenetic and fracture-modelling workflows, and (v) development of sensitivity analysis and calibration workflow.

CarboCAT (Burgess 2013) is a fully deterministic, three-dimensional numerical stratigraphic forward modelling tool designed to simulate the accumulation of heterogeneous carbonate strata on platform interiors. CarboCATLite is an open-source cellular automaton modelling software that explicitly resolves ecological competition in carbonate systems (Burgess and Pollitt 2012).

Unlike previous approaches that relied on stochastic elements to reproduce fine-scale carbonate heterogeneity (Parcell 2003; Hasler et al. 2008), CarboCAT employs a cellular automata (CA) framework, enabling complex stratigraphic behaviour to emerge exclusively from rule-based computational algorithms.

Figure 10: Eclepens Dionisos Base Case Model facies distribution in cross-section (a-b), plan-view (c) and as fence diagram (d).

The model is implemented in MATLAB and operates on a planform grid, where each cell can occupy one of four discrete states: three carbonate factory types or an empty (hiatus) state. Cell state evolution is governed by neighbourhood-based rules applied to the surrounding 24 cells. These rules approximate biological principles of spatial competition and population dynamics. To avoid preferential bias, the order in which factory types are checked for colonisation is rotated at each time step. Each factory type is assigned a distinct water-depth-dependent production profile based on the hyperbolic tangent function of Bosscher and Schlager (1992):

$$e(w) = e_m \tanh(k \exp(-dw(t)))$$

where w is water depth, e_m is maximum production rate, d is a decay constant, and k is a rate constant. Three factory configurations are defined:

- Factory 1: Shallow euphotic, high production rate, restricted to very shallow water.

- Factory 2: Deep euphotic, moderate production rate, tolerance of lower light levels.
- Factory 3: Aphotic, low production rate, depth-independent.

Production rates are further modulated by neighbourhood density, introducing spatial competition feedback into accumulation rates. A gradient-based transport algorithm redistributes a user-specified proportion of produced sediment into adjacent lower-elevation cells. Transported sediment may be assigned a distinct lithofacies, thereby generating additional heterogeneity. Transport ceases when the remaining sediment thickness falls below a threshold of 0.5 cm. Subsidence is modelled as a spatially and temporally uniform rate across the entire grid. Eustatic oscillations are represented by up to three superimposed sinusoids. During relative sea-level fall, subaerial exposure causes factory dormancy; upon reflooding, factories may reactivate, though spatial reorganisation of factory distributions is likely due to altered neighbourhood configurations. Starting from a random initial condition (spatial entropy = 0.7), the CA rapidly reduces spatial entropy to a time-averaged value of ~ 0.36 through lithofacies clustering. This demonstrates self-organisation, whereby ordered spatial patterns emerge from internal system dynamics without explicit external forcing.

The model produces complex three-dimensional stratal architectures characterised by lateral interfingering and mixed aggradational–progradational stacking patterns. Intermittent carbonate production results in a stratigraphic completeness of ~ 0.55 , consistent with observations of modern carbonate depositional surfaces (Purkis and Riegl 2005). Under conditions of differential accumulation and uncompensated accommodation, eustatic sea-level falls generate laterally discontinuous subaerial exposure surfaces, as low-lying areas of the platform remain submerged while topographically elevated areas are exposed.

Alteration of a single cell's initial facies type produces markedly divergent spatial facies distributions over time, while bulk statistical properties (e.g., spatial entropy) remain comparable. This sensitive dependence on initial conditions has significant implications for predicting carbonate facies distributions away from data control points.

CarboCAT demonstrates that significant stratigraphic heterogeneity, self-organisation, and sensitive dependence on initial conditions can arise deterministically from simple CA rules, without recourse to stochastic methods. This constitutes a meaningful advance over prior modelling approaches. However, the model currently lacks an intrinsic spatial scale, and sediment transport parameters remain poorly constrained.

4.2.7 Code Extension in Task 2.2

DionisosFlow is a diffusion-based tool designed for regional-scale basin evolution (Granjeon 1996; Granjeon and Joseph 1999) whereas CarboCATLite is a cellular-automaton model that simulates carbonate production through ecological competition (Burgess et al. 2012). As these models fundamentally differ in their formulation and resolution, a direct comparison of their outputs was deemed scientifically insufficient. Consequently, a complementary multi-scale workflow was established. In this framework, DionisosFlow defines the regional depositional architecture and broad facies belts, which act as boundary-condition inputs for CarboCATLite. CarboCATLite, in turn, refines the model at the reservoir scale by introducing high-resolution facies heterogeneity.

To achieve this integration, several modifications were made to the CarboCATLite code. DionisosFlow-derived facies grids are used as spatial and stratigraphic constraints to generate facies masks. These masks control the activity of carbonate factories within CarboCATLite, ensuring the simulation remains consistent with the regional stratigraphic architecture while generating local complexity. Figure 11 shows a side-by-side comparison between the original DionisosFlow outputs and those generated through the integrated DionisosFlow–CarboCATLite workflow. These results demonstrate the workflow's capability to provide high-resolution refinement of DionisosFlow outputs,

offering an effective intermediate solution between regional-scale commercial modelling and open-source reservoir-scale simulation.

Figure 11 Side-by-side comparison of Upper Malm stratigraphic patterns simulated using DionisosFlow (left) and further refined by the coupling of CarboCATLite model (right).

4.3 Extension of CarboCATLite Functionality

Following the initial integration, several limitations were identified in the original CarboCATLite implementation that hampered its application for reservoir modelling and its harmonisation with DionisosFlow. While DionisosFlow offers explicit control over parameters such as subsidence, carbonate production, sediment transport, and wave forcing (Granjeon and Joseph 1999; Granjeon 2014), CarboCATLite only handles a constant subsidence rate, simplified controls on time-dependent production, and a basic wave-energy formulation. To address these issues, targeted code developments were implemented to enhance the model's functionality.

The subsidence formulation was expanded to allow time-dependent multipliers to be applied to the original subsidence map. This modification enabled representing distinct tectonic or accommodation phases over time.

Similarly, production controls were refined so that individual carbonate factories could vary independently within specific time windows. This allowed for the adjustment of activity for specific factories during selected stratigraphic intervals, moving away from a single global production modifier. To further align CarboCATLite with DionisosFlow-style parameterisation, the original light-controlled production curves were replaced by depth-dependent production modifiers. These modifiers were interpolated at regular depth intervals to create continuous production curves. This improved the definition of factory-specific bathymetric windows and ensured more consistent parameter transfer between the two models.

Wave forcing was also upgraded from a simplified travelling wave front to a directional wave-energy formulation. This more flexible approach allows wave forcing to vary in both intensity and direction through time, making it possible to simulate changing hydrodynamic conditions and evaluate their impact on facies distribution and sediment redistribution.

Figure 12 qualitatively compares the output of DionisosFlow with that of the extended standalone CarboCATLite model operating independently of DionisosFlow constraints. The results indicate that the implemented extensions enabled CarboCATLite to produce depositional patterns broadly comparable to those generated by DionisosFlow when simulating the same region.

While the facies distribution from both models shows general alignment in depositional character (e.g. patchy coral reefs, ooid shoals in high-energy settings), the CarboCATLite output (right) requires calibration to achieve a closer match between the two models.

Figure 12 Side-by-side comparison of Upper Malm stratigraphic patterns simulated using DionisosFlow (left) and the upgraded CarboCATLite model (right).

Collectively, these developments significantly increased the geological flexibility of CarboCATLite, demonstrating that open-source models can be adapted to match the control capabilities of commercial software. However, the current MATLAB implementation and simplified sediment-transport physics remain limiting factors for its long-term suitability as the primary open-source platform for the project.

4.3.1 Comparative Framework and Integration of DionisosFlow and CarboCAT

Although the initial objective encompassed a direct comparative analysis of DionisosFlow and CarboCAT outputs for the Eclépens region, fundamental differences in model architecture and conceptual design render such a comparison methodologically problematic. DionisosFlow operates at regional scales, simulating large-scale stratigraphic evolution over spatial extents of tens to hundreds of kilometres and temporal spans of millions of years, with an emphasis on allocyclic controls such as base-level fluctuations and tectonic (Granjeon 2014). CarboCAT, by contrast, is specifically designed for carbonate depositional systems, employing a cellular automaton framework to simulate ecological competition among carbonate-producing communities and resolve fine-scale lithofacies heterogeneity (Masiero et al. 2021).

Given these inherent differences in scope and resolution, a complementary multi-scale approach is proposed: DionisosFlow is used to simulate regional stratigraphic architecture and platform-scale depositional trends, while CarboCAT is applied within selected intervals to resolve facies mosaics and reservoir-scale heterogeneity. To ensure consistency between the two models, key carbonate production parameters, such as maximum accumulation rates, depth of peak productivity and production-depth curve geometry are harmonised across both frameworks. Model-specific parameters, such as initial bathymetry, subsidence rate, and relative sea-level curves, are treated independently, with bathymetry anticipated to exert the dominant control on facies distribution in CarboCAT. A sensitivity analysis is planned to evaluate bathymetric influence on model outputs.

A critical challenge in coupling the two models relates to CarboCAT's cellular automaton logic, wherein facies colonisation is governed by the state of neighbouring cells. Initialising CarboCAT directly from DionisosFlow-generated facies maps, characterised by spatially uniform facies distributions, would suppress ecological variability and compromise the model's capacity to generate realistic facies mosaics. To circumvent this limitation, it is proposed to run CarboCAT on specific stratigraphic intervals using randomised initial distributions, with DionisosFlow constraining the types

of carbonate factories likely present based on regional environmental context, rather than prescribing explicit facies geometries. This methodology, however, remains hypothetical and requires systematic testing and sensitivity analysis to assess its scientific validity.

Model calibration presents an additional challenge, particularly given the scarcity of detailed sedimentological data for the Jurassic and Muschelkalk intervals in the Eclépens region. Although outcrop data from the South German Molasse Basin provide sedimentological insights into the Malm carbonates, direct application to the Geneva Basin is problematic. The two basins, despite sharing stratigraphic markers, differ markedly in terms of stratigraphic thickness, reef development, diagenetic pathways, and structural overprint. Local specific calibration is therefore essential to avoid systematic bias. Given the pronounced data limitations affecting both formations, modelling efforts are strategically focused on the Muschelkalk interval, which constitutes the primary research objective.

4.3.2 CarboKitten

Following the evaluation of CarboCat & CarboCATLite, CarboKitten was identified as a more robust open-source platform for continued development. CarboKitten is a Julia-based carbonate stratigraphic forward modelling software that builds on the CarboCAT concept while improving computational performance, modularity, transparency, and sediment-transport formulation. Its more physically consistent diffusion-based treatment of sediment redistribution made it a stronger candidate for future development within GO-Forward.

To align the software with applied reservoir workflows, several key extensions were implemented to enhance environmental forcing, ecological competition, and data export and visualisation.

4.3.3 Code Extension in Task 2.2

Subsidence was reformulated as a spatially variable field that can evolve through time, allowing differential subsidence, localised depocentres, structural compartments, or changing tectonic phases.

Carbonate production was refined, transitioning from light-dependent production curves to independent depth- and time-controlled behaviours, improving the representation of evolving carbonate production systems. Granular control over production rates was introduced, following the approach previously implemented in CarboCATLite. The cellular-automaton rules were modified to include facies-specific interaction parameters, providing greater control over the lateral continuity of facies patterns.

The wave module was upgraded to a physics-based wave-energy formulation to replace the original simplified depth-dependent wave front. The revised routine accounts for local water depth, wavelength, wave attenuation, depth-limited breaking, near-bed orbital velocity, and multiple wave directions, allowing hydrodynamic forcing to vary realistically across the evolving platform.

The option to input facies-dependent porosity-depth relationships was introduced. The code was modified so that simulated stratigraphic thicknesses can be adjusted over time as burial depth increases toward a more geologically consistent compacted record to allow comparison with well or subsurface data.

To facilitate interpretation, a post-depositional classification workflow was developed. These routines aggregate high-resolution simulation data into coarser geological blocks and calculate the relative proportions of the different carbonate factories, weighted by deposited thickness, together with representative water-depth and wave-energy values. These block-scale proportions are then compared against user-defined classification rules based on sediment composition, bathymetry, and hydrodynamic energy. Each block is assigned to the first depositional environment that satisfies these

criteria, allowing the high resolution CarboKitten output to be converted into interpretable facies or environment classes suitable for calibration, visualisation, and export to reservoir-modelling workflows. This also enables direct comparison with DionisosFlow results. Figure 13 shows a side-by-side comparison of the simulated Eclépens Malm platform before and after post-depositional facies classification.

Figure 13 Map views showing the distribution of (a) facies and (b) environments derived from the defined classification rules.

Finally, we expanded the toolset with visualisation and evaluation routines, including maps (Figure 13), fence diagrams (Figure 14), chronostratigraphic columns, thickness statistics, patch analysis, and carbonate factory proportion metrics.

Figure 14 Fence diagram of depositional environment distribution.

4.4 Towards a Hierarchical Framework

Although the extended version of CarboKitten presented above produced satisfactory results in terms of comparability with DionisosFlow outputs, modelling capabilities, and geological consistency, DionisosFlow remains better suited to generating the smooth, laterally continuous facies belts that typically characterize basin-scale facies organization. CarboKitten, by contrast, introduces a level of small-scale lateral heterogeneity that DionisosFlow does not reproduce as naturally, and that is more representative of reservoir-scale carbonate mosaics. This contrast had already been identified during our first assessment of CarboCATLite's capabilities. At that stage, we chose to leverage the complementary strengths of DionisosFlow and CarboCAT by implementing a hierarchical workflow. DionisosFlow was used to generate basin-scale depositional trends, which were then refined at smaller scale with CarboCATLite, constrained by those larger-scale trends. This multiscale approach produced the most geologically satisfactory results obtained so far. Further details are provided in the preceding sections.

We chose to implement the same general strategy within CarboKitten, with the objective of developing a complete open workflow that no longer depends on proprietary software. To achieve this, we further modified the original CarboKitten code and added the functionalities described earlier, apart from the compaction engine and the post-depositional facies classification routine. The compaction engine was not retained at this stage because it would only account for the pressure increase generated by the interval deposited during the simulation. Unless the full overlying stratigraphic succession is modelled, the resulting compacted interval thickness would therefore not be representative. Compaction is better handled later, during the diagenetic forward-modelling step, where the complete burial history can be considered. This also avoids applying compaction twice or introducing ambiguity into the workflow. The post-depositional facies classification routine was also excluded. Reclassifying model outputs using user-defined rules would overwrite the factory-level distribution generated by the model. Because such rules are inherently subjective, this would reduce confidence in the direct model output. We therefore retained the factory-level distribution as the final facies result, as it is controlled directly by the input parameters, environmental forcing, and process rules implemented in the model.

The multiscale framework was implemented to separate regional-scale depositional organization from local factory-scale carbonate accumulation. The objective is to use a first, lower-detail model to generate broad depositional trends, then use those trends to condition a second, higher-detail model in which individual carbonate factories interact with local environmental conditions, cellular-automaton rules, and active-layer transport.

The workflow is organized in two main modelling stages. The first stage is a regional trend simulation. In this model, the facies classes are not intended to represent final lithofacies directly. Instead, they represent broad depositional environments or tendencies, such as ooid-shoal-prone areas, coral-reef-prone areas or lagoonal areas, amongst others. These regional trends are controlled mainly by the imposed bathymetry, subsidence, sea-level history, and facies-specific production windows. This allows the regional model to simulate first-order environmental organization over the platform without requiring the final factory-scale facies architecture to be resolved at this stage.

An intermediate probability-block construction step converts the regional run into a three-dimensional stratigraphic probability block. This block describes which regional trend is most likely at each horizontal position and stratigraphic level. During this conversion, an initial burn-in interval can be discarded to avoid using the early numerical adjustment phase of the regional model. The resulting probabilities can also be smoothed laterally over a user-defined radius and number of passes, which controls whether the regional trends are expressed as sharp local patches or broader depositional belts.

Because the regional trend classes and the factory-scale facies are not necessarily the same, a transition matrix is used to convert regional-trend probabilities into factory-facies probabilities. For example, an ooid shoal trend can be mapped mostly to the ooids factory facies, but with smaller probabilities assigned to grains, mud, corals, or sabkha. This matrix provides an explicit and interpretable link between regional depositional tendencies and the detailed facies assemblage used in the factory-scale model.

The second modelling stage is the trend-conditioned factory run. This stage combines the trend-conditioning component with the native CarboKitten competition framework. At each timestep, the model evaluates the current sediment height at each grid cell and samples the corresponding layer of the probability block. The probability prior acts on the factory model in two ways. First, it can bias the cellular-automaton state through trend-guided seeding and replacement. This affects which active factory facies are allowed to occupy a cell. The strength of this control can be tuned via user-controlled parameters. Second, the prior can weight facies production directly. In this case, the total local production is preserved, but the distribution of production among facies is shifted toward those favoured by the probability block. This distinction allows the user to decide whether the regional trend mainly controls facies occupation, production partitioning, or both. The factory facies themselves retain their own local rules. Each factory can be active or passive, can have a specific neighbourhood radius, and can have its own viability and activation ranges. These rules control the patch size and persistence of factory-scale facies. Figure 15 summarizes this hierarchical workflow, from regional trend generation to finer-scale factory-level conditioning.

Figure 15 Simplified hierarchical workflow illustrating the two main stages of the multiscale modelling framework. In the first stage, regional simulations are used to generate probability maps representing broad depositional trends, shown on the left. These maps are then used as priors to condition a finer-scale factory-level simulation, together with factory-specific production curves and competition rules. The resulting output is a mosaic-like factory distribution with enhanced small-scale lateral heterogeneity, shown on the right.

Overall, the framework implements a hierarchical modelling strategy. The regional model captures broad depositional organization, the probability-block builder converts that organization into a stratigraphic prior, and the factory-scale model uses that prior while still allowing local competition rules, environmental production, and active-layer transport to shape the final stratigraphy. This makes the workflow flexible enough to preserve large-scale geological trends while still producing local patchiness, facies competition, transport effects, and stratigraphic architecture at the factory scale.

These developments are currently being prepared for integration into the official CarboKitten codebase, which is developed in the context of the EU-funded Horizon Europe ERC Starting Grant MindTheGap “Quantifying the completeness of the stratigraphic record and its role in reconstructing the tempo and mode of evolution” (ERC, MindTheGap, StG project no 101041077)

4.5 Data Assimilation Capabilities

4.5.1 Software interfaces and workflow interoperability

Another aim of Task 2.2 involved developing interfaces between the various modelling tools utilized in the GO-Forward workflow. This requires establishing robust format conversion routines between tools not originally designed for interoperability.

We developed routines to convert DionisosFlow outputs into formats compatible with CarboCATLite and CarboKitten. These processes involve parsing GOCAD TSURF surfaces and Eclipse GRDECL grids, extracting bathymetry, subsidence, and facies data, and interpolating this information onto regular modelling grids for the open-source models. Once the simulations are completed, additional routines export results from CarboCATLite and CarboKitten back into structured grid formats. Specifically, outputs are converted into Eclipse-style GRDECL grids to maintain spatial consistency with the original geometry. This ensures that facies models generated by open-source SFM tools can be imported into industry-standard software such as Petrel, JewelSuite, or Golem for subsequent petrophysical, diagenetic, or fracture-network analysis. Interoperability is essential for the GO-Forward project as it links the SFM module to the broader integrated modelling chain. It allows the depositional architecture, facies proportions, and spatial heterogeneity generated by SFM to serve as critical inputs for subsequent diagenetic and fracture-forward modelling tasks.

4.5.2 Sensitivity Analysis and Calibration Workflow

The sensitivity analysis and calibration strategy are currently under active development. A preliminary hybrid workflow has been implemented to quantify model uncertainty and determine the range of plausible stratigraphic outcomes.

The SFM involves 39 input parameters, which impact model results. The initial stage involved a two-stage Morris sensitivity analysis to reduce this parameter space. To maintain computational efficiency while preserving geological significance, parameters were initially grouped by process rather than testing them individually. Each group represented a dominant mechanism controlling the model response. Parameters were mapped from normalised values to physical ranges using linear, log-uniform, or rounded integer functions as appropriate. The first pass identified the most influential process groups, specifically production intensity and post-depositional processes. In the second pass, these groups were expanded into individual parameters, while less influential controls remained grouped. This approach allowed the selection of dominant variables to focus on for the subsequent Monte Carlo analysis: basin forcing, specific factory production rates, neighbourhood radius, and disintegration rate.

Monte Carlo samples were generated using Latin hypercube sampling and processed through CarboKitten. Outputs were consistently post-processed to extract platform thickness, facies proportions, and 3D patch metrics. The resulting 884 valid realisations were summarised using descriptive statistics for each output metric, including sample size, mean, standard deviation, and selected quantiles. Output distributions were inspected using Kernel Density Estimation (KDE) plots, as shown in Figure 16. Sensitivity within the Monte Carlo ensemble was assessed using rank-based measures, including Spearman correlation and partial rank correlation coefficients (PRCC), computed between selected input parameters and key output metrics (Figure 17). Convergence and stability of the Monte Carlo results were evaluated by comparing output quantiles and PRCC rankings computed from subsets of the ensemble to those computed from the full sample. This analysis was used to verify that the chosen sample size was sufficient to stabilise both output distributions and sensitivity rankings for the selected parameters.

Figure 16 Output distributions (histograms / KDE) from Monte Carlo simulations.

Figure 17 Spearman (left) and PRCC (right) sensitivity heatmaps. Parameters include G1 (basin forcing), P2, P3 and P4 (respectively corals, carbonate mud and carbonate grains production rates), G5 (neighbourhood radius) and P6 (disintegration rate).

The Spearman and PRCC sensitivity heatmaps in Figure 17 show that mean platform thickness is mainly controlled by the disintegration rate. This means that preserved thickness depends strongly on how sediment is reworked, removed, and redistributed after production. Basin forcing and carbonate mud production have a secondary influence. Ooid proportion is particularly sensitive to both neighbourhood radius and carbonate mud production. This suggests that ooid development is mainly controlled by competition between carbonate factories. As mud production increases, mud-producing factories occupy more depositional space and reduce the area available for ooid-prone deposits. This limits the ability of ooids to establish and persist. This competitive effect is further amplified by the ooid neighbourhood radius, which defines the spatial extent over which ooid factories can compete, spread, and maintain their position in the model. Carbonate mud proportion is controlled by its own production rate, carbonate grain production, and neighbourhood radius. Carbonate grain proportion shows the opposite link. It is mainly controlled by carbonate grain production, but it also responds to carbonate mud production and basin forcing. This pattern suggests competition between fine- and coarse-grained factories. Because they occupy similar depositional niches, stronger production by one factory can reduce the space available for the other. Coral proportion is mainly controlled by neighbourhood radius indicating that coral development is shaped more by ecological competition and spatial persistence than by coral production rate alone. This likely reflects the overlap between its production window and those of other factories. Unlike ooids, its production rate does not greatly exceed that of competing factories, which limits its ability to establish and persist when other factories thrive.

The output histograms in Figure 16 highlight the model's sensitivity to small variations in initial conditions. For ooids and corals, the high frequency of zero values indicates that these facies often fail to establish themselves. This suggests they are governed by 'all-or-nothing' thresholds: they are either outcompeted early on or successfully expand into the varied patterns seen in the distribution tails. By contrast, carbonate mud shows a strong rightward skew, confirming it as the most persistent and dominant facies. This dominance likely arises from the fact that mud establishes easily and persists and is consistent with the fact that mud production rate directly influences other facies proportions as shown in Figure 17. The mirroring trends between the mud and grain histograms further reflect this, showing their mutual sensitivity to one another's production rates. While individual facies vary significantly due to spatial competition, the mean platform thickness follows a more stable, bell-shaped curve. This indicates that while the specific sediment composition changes between simulations, the total volume produced remains a relatively steady balance between accommodation and overall growth.

Despite providing useful insights into the dynamics of the model, this hybrid sensitivity analysis method has several pitfalls. Grouping of parameters is based on expert judgment, which is prone to bias. This oversimplification likely missed critical, non-linear parameter interactions that only emerge when variables are studied independently. To address these limitations and provide a more rigorous assessment of the model, we require a more robust, independent approach. Sobol analysis is a variance-based global sensitivity method that assigns fractions of the model's output variance to specific inputs (Saltelli et al. 2008). Unlike the Morris method, it captures high-order, non-linear interactions and provides a "total-effect index" for each variable without requiring subjective grouping. In the next phases of the project, we will therefore transition towards that approach.

5 Data Availability

All codes, software extensions, and workflows developed within Task 2.2, including the extended CarboKitten and CarboCATLite implementations, the stochastic patch reef modelling tools, format conversion interfaces, and sensitivity analysis scripts, will be made publicly available through the GO-Forward Zenodo community repository, (<https://zenodo.org/communities/go-forward/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>), ensuring full transparency, reproducibility, and open access for the broader scientific and industrial community. For CarboKitten, a pull request has been submitted to the original GitHub repository [GitHub - MindTheGap-ERC/CarboKitten.jl: Julia implementation of carbonate platform model · GitHub](#), proposing the integration of all code extensions developed within Task 2.2 into the main codebase.

6 Conclusions

Task 2.2 of the GO-Forward project has successfully achieved its primary objectives: the systematic evaluation of open-source Stratigraphic Forward Modelling (SFM) tools against the commercial benchmark DionisosFlow, the development and extension of open-source SFM capabilities for carbonate systems, and the preliminary implementation of data assimilation and calibration workflows.

An extensive review of available SFM codebases identified CarboKitten, a Julia-based reimplement of CarboCAT, as the most promising open-source platform for further development within the project. Its open licensing, high-performance programming language, modular architecture, and physically consistent diffusion-based sediment transport formulation provide a robust foundation for applied reservoir-scale stratigraphic modelling.

Significant code extensions were implemented across CarboCATLite and CarboKitten, including spatiotemporally variable subsidence, independent depth- and time-controlled carbonate production, directional wave-energy forcing, porosity-depth compaction, rule-based facies classification, and comprehensive visualisation tools (fence diagrams, maps, chronostratigraphic columns). These developments substantially enhanced the geological realism and operational flexibility of the open-source tools, bringing their parameterisation capabilities closer to those offered by DionisosFlow.

Additionally, complementary tools were developed for modelling isolated carbonate build-ups, including a Python-based stochastic point cloud algorithm and a Blender Geometry Nodes framework. These tools address a critical limitation of DionisosFlow, its inability to resolve the stochastic spatial distribution of patch reefs and provide direct inputs for reservoir modelling, variogram calculation, and multiple point statistics workflows.

The Eclepens case study (Oxfordian carbonate platform, Swiss Jura) served as the primary test site for benchmarking. Results demonstrate that DionisosFlow remains the preferred tool for regional-scale modelling due to its mature functionality and graphical user interface. However, the extended CarboKitten code now provides a scientifically credible open-source alternative capable of resolving reservoir-scale facies heterogeneity. A complementary multi-scale workflow, where DionisosFlow defines regional stratigraphic architecture and CarboKitten resolves fine-scale heterogeneity, has been established and validated. Software interfaces enabling format conversion between DionisosFlow, CarboCATLite, CarboKitten, and industry-standard reservoir modelling tools (Eclipse GRDECL, GOCAD TSURF) were developed, ensuring interoperability across the GO-Forward integrated modelling chain.

Regarding data assimilation, a hybrid sensitivity analysis workflow combining Morris screening and Monte Carlo simulation was implemented. Results reveal that model behaviour is governed by complex, nonlinear interactions between parameters, particularly basin forcing, production rates, neighbourhood radius, and disintegration rate. The analysis confirms that manual calibration is insufficient for this parameter space. The transition towards variance-based global sensitivity methods (Sobol analysis) and AI-driven optimisation is identified as essential for future calibration efforts. In summary, Task 2.2 has established the methodological and open-source software foundations for stratigraphic forward modelling within the GO-Forward project. The open-source tools developed offer a transparent, publicly accessible, and extensible alternative to commercial software, reducing dependency on proprietary solutions while enabling reproducible research in geothermal reservoir characterisation. Future work will focus on continued validation through additional case studies, implementation of Sobol-based sensitivity analysis, and integration of machine learning methods for automated calibration and uncertainty quantification.

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